

Angelo Leogrando*^o

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

^oLUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Email: leogrando.cultore@lum.it

The Infrastructure Index at Global Level

The Infrastructure Index in the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII) is a composite measure that evaluates various aspects of a country's infrastructure, which are essential for supporting innovation. This index focuses on three main components: information and communication technologies (ICT), which assess Internet penetration, broadband availability, mobile network coverage, and the adoption of digital technologies by businesses and consumers, as well as the quality and accessibility of ICT services, which are fundamental for developing innovation capacities. It also includes general infrastructure, which encompasses access to basic services such as electricity, water, and transportation. High-quality general infrastructure is crucial for an innovative economy, as it facilitates the production, distribution, and sale of goods and services, as well as improves the mobility of people, goods, and services within and outside a country. Lastly, sustainable ecology evaluates a country's policies and practices that promote a sustainable economy and the efficient use of resources, including the use of renewable energies and the management of natural resources. An economy that invests in sustainable infrastructure is considered more innovative, as it prepares for a long-term global economic environment that prioritizes sustainability. The Infrastructure Index is, therefore, an essential measure within the GII, as it reflects how well a country's infrastructure can support innovation and, ultimately, economic growth. The data refers to the period from 2013 to 2022.

The global Infrastructure Index in 2022 clearly shows a strong predominance of Nordic countries and other advanced economies, with Sweden ranking first with a score of 67, followed by Norway (66.5) and Finland (65.9). These countries are known for their excellent infrastructure, characterized by high penetration of information and communication technologies (ICT), efficient transportation infrastructures, and a strong commitment to sustainability. Beyond the Nordic countries, other developed economies such as Switzerland (65.7), Denmark (64.3), and Hong Kong SAR, China (63.7) stand out for their advanced infrastructures, which include high-quality ICT services, access to essential services, and well-developed transportation networks. These countries are often considered global leaders in innovation, and their strong positioning in the Infrastructure Index reflects their ability to support and foster innovation. The United Arab Emirates (63.2) and the United Kingdom (62.9) represent other economies that rank high on the list, highlighting how modern infrastructure is essential not only for countries traditionally associated with innovation but also for rapidly growing economies seeking to establish themselves on the global stage. Austria (62.7) and Estonia (61.6) closely follow, demonstrating how even smaller or transitioning countries can excel in building infrastructures that support innovation. East Asia is significantly represented by Singapore (61.4), Japan (61.3), and South Korea (60.3), all of which have heavily invested in information technologies, transportation infrastructure, and environmental sustainability. These countries have historically combined strong governance with public and private investments in advanced infrastructure, thus ensuring an environment conducive to innovation. In the European context, Ireland (60.1) and the Netherlands (60.1) also show solid infrastructures, reflecting a long tradition of investments in transportation and ICT, as well as a regulatory environment that fosters innovation. Spain (59.8) and France (59) maintain prominent positions, although slightly lower than European

leaders, indicating solid infrastructural potential but with room for improvement. Below the 60-point threshold, we find Australia (58.8), the United States (58.7), and Germany (57.7), countries that, despite having high-level infrastructures, might be limited by issues such as resource distribution disparities or challenges related to modernizing their existing infrastructures. These countries, despite their relatively low scores, continue to be global leaders in innovation, demonstrating that infrastructure is only one of the elements contributing to innovative success. Further down the list, Romania (54.8) and Bulgaria (54.7) represent Eastern Europe, with developing infrastructures that are beginning to compete with those of Western Europe. Asia is represented by economies like China (57.5) and Malaysia (48.6), which have made significant progress in infrastructure but continue to face challenges of uneven development and regional disparities. Middle Eastern economies such as Qatar (57.1), Bahrain (55.8), and Kuwait (54) also rank in the upper half of the list, showing the effect of strategic investments in infrastructure to support economic diversification and reduce dependence on natural resources. However, many Middle Eastern and North African economies are still in a developmental phase, with scores like Oman (46.9) and Algeria (31.1) reflecting the need to improve infrastructures to compete globally. Emerging economies in Latin America, such as Brazil (43.9) and Mexico (44.2), highlight the infrastructural challenges they face, including insufficient investments in ICT and transportation infrastructures, which limit their ability to sustain innovation growth. Similarly, Sub-Saharan African countries like Ghana (34.3), Kenya (30.3), and Ethiopia (23.9) are towards the bottom of the list, where weak infrastructures, problems accessing basic services, and a lack of investment in modern technologies represent significant obstacles to their innovative development. Finally, countries like Afghanistan, Guinea, and Madagascar, which occupy the lowest positions on the list, highlight how the lack of adequate infrastructure is a critical obstacle to economic development and innovation. These countries face enormous challenges in building basic infrastructure that can support education, healthcare, and access to technologies, all essential elements for integrating into the global innovation economy.

The global Infrastructure Index between 2013 and 2022 shows significant improvements in many emerging and developing economies, which have often faced substantial challenges in improving their infrastructures. A striking example is Uzbekistan, which saw an increase of 19.3 points, rising from 22.4 in 2013 to 41.7 in 2022, with an impressive percentage variation of 86.16%. This improvement reflects the country's efforts to modernize its infrastructures, particularly in the energy and transport sectors, crucial for supporting economic growth and improving quality of life. In Africa, countries like Burkina Faso and Mozambique have shown remarkable progress, with percentage variations of 102.22% and 88.89%, respectively. These improvements, although starting from relatively low bases, highlight these nations' commitment to expanding access to basic services and improving transport and communication networks, fundamental elements for socio-economic development. However, the challenges remain enormous, and future progress will depend on the ability to attract sustainable investments and effectively manage resources. In Europe, countries like Slovakia, Slovenia, and Croatia have shown significant improvements, with increases of over 10 points in the index. These countries have benefited from European Union structural funds and targeted policies to modernize their infrastructures. Access to advanced technologies and the implementation of effective transport networks have contributed to improving not only physical infrastructure but also to creating a more favorable environment for innovation. The situation in Asia presents diverse scenarios. While countries like Vietnam and Indonesia have seen improvements of 45.55% and 49.14%, respectively, reflecting rapid growth and the expansion of urban and digital infrastructures, other nations like Mongolia have seen a slight decline in the Infrastructure Index. This suggests that

despite significant progress in some areas, challenges related to access inequality and infrastructure quality remain, particularly in more remote regions. In the Middle East, significant improvements in countries like Kuwait (52.97%) and Qatar (24.13%) highlight the strategic importance attributed to infrastructure development in these resource-rich economies. Investment in advanced infrastructures has been a pillar of economic diversification strategies, aimed at reducing dependence on oil and gas exports and creating more resilient and sustainable economies. On the other side of the spectrum, some of the most advanced economies have seen more modest improvements. For example, Germany and the United States saw increases in the index of 7.85% and 11.81%, respectively. These countries, already equipped with highly developed infrastructures, face challenges related to modernizing existing infrastructures and managing complex and extensive networks. Furthermore, these data may reflect the attainment of a certain saturation point in infrastructural development, where incremental improvements become more difficult and costly. An interesting case is represented by South Korea, which recorded a slight decline of 0.4 points in the index. Although this country remains a global leader in innovation and technological development, this figure may indicate challenges related to the sustainability and maintenance of high-level infrastructures, as well as reflect changes in political and economic priorities. Brazil, with an improvement of 18.01%, represents an example of a developing country making progress but continuing to face significant obstacles. The growth of infrastructures in Brazil has been uneven, with significant investments in some regions and sectors, while other areas remain neglected. Geographic diversity and economic disparities represent enormous challenges for such a vast and complex country. In terms of relative progress, countries like Albania (48.87%) and Armenia (56.47%) have shown substantial improvements, reflecting the benefits derived from reform policies and integration with more advanced regional economies. These countries have significantly invested in key infrastructures, such as transportation networks and telecommunications, to improve their economic competitiveness.

Economic policies aimed at improving the Infrastructure Index must be multidimensional and long-term oriented since infrastructures represent the backbone on which a country's entire economic and innovative ecosystem is based. Solid infrastructure not only facilitates the production and distribution of goods and services but is also crucial for a nation's global competitiveness. Therefore, improving the Infrastructure Index requires an integrated approach involving investments in advanced technologies, modernization of transportation networks, expansion of access to basic services, and promotion of environmental sustainability. One of the fundamental pillars for improving the Infrastructure Index is investment in information and communication technologies (ICT). Economies that wish to remain competitive must adopt strategies that incentivize broadband expansion, improve mobile network coverage, and promote the integration of digital technologies across all sectors. For example, countries like South Korea and Singapore have achieved very high levels in the Infrastructure Index precisely due to their advanced ICT networks, which allow for rapid innovation diffusion and greater operational efficiency. Policies that encourage collaboration between the public and private sectors can accelerate these developments, making a more favorable environment for innovation possible. The modernization of transportation infrastructures is another crucial area. Efficient roads, railways, ports, and airports not only facilitate commerce and internal mobility but also enhance integration with international markets. To improve the Infrastructure Index, governments must invest in infrastructure projects that not only meet current needs but are also designed to address future demographic and economic challenges. This includes the adoption of smart technologies in transportation, such as intelligent traffic systems and advanced logistics, which can significantly improve the efficiency of transportation networks. Access to basic services, such as

electricity, clean water, and waste management, is a key indicator of infrastructural development. Many developing countries that score low on the Infrastructure Index still face significant challenges in these areas. Economic policies must, therefore, focus on expanding these services, particularly in rural areas and disadvantaged communities, through investments in essential infrastructure and the adoption of innovative solutions such as decentralized renewable energy and desalination technologies. For example, Sub-Saharan Africa has enormous potential for solar energy, and policies that incentivize the installation of solar panels in rural areas can significantly improve access to electricity and, consequently, the Infrastructure Index. Environmental sustainability is another essential component of economic policies aimed at improving the Infrastructure Index. In an era of climate change, infrastructures must be resilient and sustainable. Economic policies should promote the efficient use of natural resources, reduce carbon emissions, and adopt sustainable practices across all economic sectors. This includes incentivizing renewable energies, such as wind and solar, and promoting green infrastructure, such as low-energy buildings and sustainable public transportation systems. Additionally, sustainable urban planning, which integrates parks and green spaces within cities, not only improves the quality of life but also helps mitigate the effects of climate change, making cities more resilient. Regulatory reforms are also crucial. Regulations must facilitate investments in infrastructure while ensuring that these investments are sustainable and socially equitable. For example, public-private partnership (PPP) policies can be extremely effective in mobilizing resources for large-scale infrastructure projects, especially in developing countries. However, it is essential that these partnerships are well-structured, with a clear definition of the roles and responsibilities of each party, to avoid conflicts and ensure the long-term sustainability of the projects. Education and training are fundamental elements for supporting infrastructure. A well-trained workforce is essential for the construction, maintenance, and innovation of infrastructures. Governments must therefore invest in educational and technical training programs that prepare workers for key infrastructure sectors, such as civil engineering, ICT, and environmental management. Furthermore, promoting research and development (R&D) in universities and research centers can lead to significant innovations that improve the efficiency and sustainability of infrastructures. Economic policies must also consider inclusivity. Infrastructures must be accessible to all, regardless of income, geographical location, or other socio-economic conditions. Inequalities in access to infrastructure can perpetuate poverty and limit opportunities for economic growth. Therefore, policies should ensure that investments in infrastructure are distributed equitably and that the benefits derived from infrastructures reach all communities, particularly the most disadvantaged. Infrastructure development strategies must also be flexible and adaptable to changing circumstances. The COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated the importance of resilient infrastructures and the need to be prepared for unforeseen events. Countries must develop infrastructures that can quickly adapt to new situations, such as increased demand for healthcare services or the need to ensure the continuity of supply chains during crises. Finally, international cooperation is essential for the success of infrastructural policies. Many infrastructure-related challenges, such as climate change, water resource management, and global connectivity, require cross-border cooperation. Countries must work together to develop common standards, share best practices, and coordinate investments in infrastructure projects that have a regional or global impact. For example, cross-border infrastructure projects, such as international railway networks or joint water projects, can significantly improve the Infrastructure Index for the countries involved and promote sustainable economic growth in the long term.

In conclusion, the value of the Infrastructure Index grew by an average of 26.88% between 2013 and 2022 for the countries considered. However, there are countries where the Infrastructure Index has grown much more than the average, as in the case of Mali with a value of 108.77%, Burkina Faso with 102.22%, Mozambique with 88.88%, Uzbekistan with 86.16%, and Ghana with 81.48%. There are also countries where the growth of the Infrastructure Index has been much more moderate and, in some cases, negative, as in the case of Niger with 4.00%, Singapore with 3.71%, Hong Kong with 0.47%, South Korea with -0.65%, and Mongolia with -1.38%. These variations reflect the diverse economic policies and challenges faced by different nations. For example, countries with significant increases in the Infrastructure Index, such as Mali and Burkina Faso, have likely implemented aggressive policies to expand access to basic services and improve transportation networks, addressing long-standing infrastructural deficits. These efforts are critical for fostering economic growth and improving the quality of life in these regions. Conversely, countries with smaller increases or declines in the Infrastructure Index, such as Singapore and South Korea, might already have highly developed infrastructures, where further improvements are more challenging and costly, or they might face issues related to sustainability and maintenance. As global challenges such as climate change and economic inequality continue to evolve, it will be crucial for countries to adopt forward-looking policies that prioritize sustainable and inclusive infrastructure development. By doing so, nations can not only improve their Infrastructure Index but also enhance their resilience to future challenges and ensure long-term economic prosperity.

References

- Arnone, M.; Legrande, A. (2024). The Green Trilemma: Energy Efficiency, Banking Stability and Climate Risk in the ESG Context at World Level.
- Arnone, M.; Legrande, A. (2024). The People You Can Count on in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4873511.
- Arnone, M.; Legrande, A. (2024). The Sustainability of the Factoring Chain in Europe in the Light of the Integration of ESG Factors. Available at SSRN 4880150.
- Arnone, M., Angelillis, B., Costantiello, A., & Legrande, A. (2024). Graduates, Training and Employment Across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4850961.

Arnone, M., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Access to Credit in the Context of the ESG Framework at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4912994.

Arnone, M., Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2024). Banking Stability in the ESG Framework Across Italian Regions (No. 121452). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. *Discover Global Society*, 2(1), 1.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In *Data-Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability* (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Companies with at least 10 Employees Selling Online across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4785815.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions. Available at SSRN.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4772381.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Regular Internet Users Across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4782193.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771131.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4771132.

Leogrande, A., Resta, E., & Costantiello, A. (2024). The Renunciation of Healthcare Services in the Italian Regions in the ESG Context. Available at SSRN 4746676.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Air Pollution in the ESG Model at the World Level. In *Intersecting Environmental Social Governance and AI for Business Sustainability* (pp. 93-122). IGI Global.

Magazzino, C., Madaleno, M., Waqas, M., & Leogrande, A. (2024). Exploring the determinants of methane emissions from a worldwide perspective using panel data and machine learning analyses. *Environmental Pollution*, 348, 123807.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP*, 28(3,), 1-22.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP*, 28(3,), 1-13.

Resta, E., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3,), 1-15.

Resta, E., Logroscino, G., Tafuri, S., Peter, P., Noviello, C., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Mental Health Index across the Italian Regions in the ESG Context (No. 3cztm). Center for Open Science.

Resta, E., Resta, O., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The hospital emigration to another region in the light of the environmental, social and governance model in Italy during the period 2004-2021. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 1880.

Salvatore, D., Magazzino, C., Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2024). The economic determinants of world disorder events: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 46(4), 740-756.